

Prevalence of Left Ventricular Diastolic Dysfunction in Patients with Subclinical Hypothyroidism

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Abstract:

Background: Elevated thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH) levels with normal free thyroxine (T4) and triiodothyronine (T3) levels are the hallmarks of subclinical hypothyroidism. Although it is frequently asymptomatic, there is growing evidence connecting it to anomalies in the cardiovascular system, such as left ventricular diastolic dysfunction (LVDD). The study aims to ascertain the frequency of subclinical hypothyroidism in individuals with left ventricular diastolic dysfunction and to investigate the clinical and echocardiographic features that are related to this condition.

Methods: A total of 100 participants diagnosed with subclinical hypothyroidism were included. Data were collected through structured questionnaires, medical records, and echocardiographic assessments. Statistical analysis was accomplished using SPSS version 23.0.

Results: Three-quarters of the subjects had LVDD. Compared to patients without LVDD, individuals with LVDD had considerably lower free T3 levels (3.0 ± 0.4 vs. 3.2 ± 0.5 pg/mL, $p=0.04$) and significantly higher TSH levels (6.1 ± 1.3 vs. 5.6 ± 1.1 mIU/L, $p=0.03$). Patients with LVDD exhibit decreased relaxation and elevated filling pressures, as seen by significant differences in echocardiographic parameters such as the E/A ratio, deceleration time, left atrial volume index, and E/e' ratio between the groups.

Conclusion: A high frequency of LVDD is linked to subclinical hypothyroidism. In this population, diastolic dysfunction may emerge as a result of elevated TSH and free T3 levels. Frequent cardiovascular evaluations are advised for people with subclinical hypothyroidism in order to diagnose and treat LVDD early.

Recommendations: Healthcare providers should consider routine cardiovascular screening for patients with subclinical hypothyroidism to identify and manage LVDD early. Further research is needed to explore the underlying mechanisms and potential therapeutic interventions for diastolic dysfunction in this population.

Keywords: Subclinical hypothyroidism, Left ventricular diastolic dysfunction, TSH, Echocardiography, Cardiovascular risk.

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Introduction

Subclinical hypothyroidism (SCH) is a common endocrine disorder characterized by elevated serum thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH) levels with normal free thyroxine (T4) and triiodothyronine (T3) levels. It is often asymptomatic, but its potential impact on various organ systems, including the cardiovascular system, has been increasingly recognized. The cardiovascular system is particularly sensitive to thyroid hormone levels, and even subtle changes in thyroid function can have significant clinical implications. Recent studies have highlighted the potential association between subclinical hypothyroidism and various cardiovascular abnormalities, including diastolic dysfunction, which is an early indicator of heart failure and other cardiovascular events.

The term "left ventricular diastolic dysfunction" (LVDD) describes the heart's inability to adequately fill and relax during diastole. If not recognised and treated properly, it can result in severe morbidity and mortality and frequently serves as a prelude to more obvious forms of heart failure. Thyroid hormones are known to be critical for myocardial contractility, vascular resistance, and total cardiac output, and their association to cardiac performance is well-established [1]. SCH has been connected to endothelial dysfunction, elevated arterial stiffness, and modifications in lipid metabolism, all of which raise the risk of cardiovascular disease.

Although the prevalence of LVDD has been investigated in a number of epidemiological studies

across different demographics, there is a dearth of information that particularly looks at this disease in individuals with SCH. According to a meta-analysis, heart failure, especially heart failure with maintained ejection fraction, which is directly linked to diastolic dysfunction, is more common in people with SCH [2]. According to a different study, people with SCH were more likely than people with euthyroid conditions to have left ventricular hypertrophy and poor diastolic function [3].

Given the growing body of evidence linking subclinical hypothyroidism with cardiovascular abnormalities, it is imperative to further investigate the specific prevalence and characteristics of LVDD in this patient population. Early detection and management of diastolic dysfunction in patients with SCH could potentially mitigate the risk of progression to more severe cardiovascular conditions.

This study aimed at determining the prevalence of left ventricular diastolic dysfunction in patients with subclinical hypothyroidism.

Methodology

Study Design: A prospective observational study.

Study Setting: The study took place during a period of February 2023 to February 2024 at Rajshree Medical Research Institute, Bareilly, India.

Participants: The study included a total of 100 participants diagnosed with subclinical hypothyroidism.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Patients aged 18 years and above.
2. Patients diagnosed with SCH

Exclusion Criteria

1. Patients with overt hypothyroidism.

2. Patients with a history of cardiovascular diseases.
3. Pregnant women.
4. Patients with other systemic illnesses such as diabetes, hypertension, and chronic kidney disease.
5. Patients on medication that could affect thyroid function or cardiac performance.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, participants were randomly selected from those attending the outpatient department of Rajshree Medical Research Institute. Information bias was reduced by using standardized diagnostic criteria and data collection methods.

Data Collection: A systematic questionnaire and an examination of medical records were used to gather data. The following information was acquired:

- Demographic information
- Medical history
- Laboratory test results (TSH, free T4, free T3)
- Echocardiographic parameters to assess left ventricular diastolic function

Procedure: Participants underwent a thorough clinical examination. Blood samples were collected to measure thyroid function tests. Echocardiography was performed to assess left ventricular diastolic function. Data were recorded and compiled in a standardized format.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analysed with SPSS 23.0. Participants' demographic and clinical features were summarised using descriptive statistics. A p-value <0.05 indicated statistical significance.

Result

The study comprised 100 individuals who had been diagnosed with subclinical hypothyroidism.

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics

Characteristic	Mean $\pm$ SD / N (%)
Age (years)	45.3 $\pm$ 12.7
Gender	
- Male	30 (30%)
- Female	70 (70%)
BMI (kg/m ²)	26.5 $\pm$ 4.2
TSH (mIU/L)	5.8 $\pm$ 1.2
Free T4 (ng/dL)	1.2 $\pm$ 0.3
Free T3 (pg/mL)	3.1 $\pm$ 0.5
Hypertension	20 (20%)
Diabetes Mellitus	15 (15%)
Smoking	10 (10%)

The prevalence of LVDD among the study participants was found to be 32% (32 out of 100 participants). The echocardiographic parameters of the participants are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2: Echocardiographic Parameters

Parameters	Mean $\pm$ SD / N (%)
E/A Ratio	0.9 $\pm$ 0.3
Deceleration Time (ms)	220 $\pm$ 35
Left Atrial Volume Index (mL/m ²)	28 $\pm$ 8
E/e' Ratio	12 $\pm$ 4

Table 3 compares the demographic, clinical, and echocardiographic characteristics between participants with and without left ventricular diastolic dysfunction.

Table 3: Comparison Between Participants with and without Diastolic Dysfunction

Characteristic	Diastolic Dysfunction	No Diastolic Dysfunction	p-value
Age (years)	48.1 $\pm$ 11.4	43.8 $\pm$ 13.2	0.07
Gender			
- Male	10	20	0.64
- Female	22	48	
BMI (kg/m ²)	27.8 $\pm$ 4.1	25.9 $\pm$ 4.3	0.05
TSH (mIU/L)	6.1 $\pm$ 1.3	5.6 $\pm$ 1.1	0.03
Free T4 (ng/dL)	1.1 $\pm$ 0.3	1.2 $\pm$ 0.3	0.15
Free T3 (pg/mL)	3.0 $\pm$ 0.4	3.2 $\pm$ 0.5	0.04
E/A Ratio	0.7 $\pm$ 0.2	1.0 $\pm$ 0.3	<0.001
Deceleration Time (ms)	240 $\pm$ 30	210 $\pm$ 35	<0.001
Left Atrial Volume Index (mL/m ²)	30 $\pm$ 8	27 $\pm$ 7	0.04
E/e' Ratio	15 $\pm$ 4	11 $\pm$ 3	<0.001

Discussion

The study included 100 participants diagnosed with subclinical hypothyroidism and aimed to determine the prevalence of LVDD among them. The demographic and clinical characteristics revealed a mean age of 45.3 years, with a predominance of female participants (70%). The average BMI was 26.5 kg/m², and the mean TSH level was 5.8 mIU/L, indicating subclinical hypothyroidism. The study population also included individuals with hypertension (20%) and diabetes mellitus (15%).

The prevalence of LVDD was found to be 32%, indicating that nearly one-third of the participants with subclinical hypothyroidism exhibited diastolic dysfunction. This high prevalence suggests a significant burden of cardiovascular abnormalities in this population.

Echocardiographic parameters showed notable differences between participants with and without diastolic dysfunction. Those with DD had a lower E/A ratio (0.7 $\pm$ 0.2 vs. 1.0 $\pm$ 0.3, $p < 0.001$) and longer deceleration time (240 $\pm$ 30 ms vs. 210 $\pm$ 35 ms, $p < 0.001$). Additionally, the left atrial volume index and E/e' ratio were higher in participants with diastolic dysfunction (30 $\pm$ 8 mL/m² vs. 27 $\pm$ 7 mL/m², $p = 0.04$; and 15 $\pm$ 4 vs. 11 $\pm$ 3, $p < 0.001$, respectively). These findings indicate impaired relaxation and increased filling pressures in the left ventricle among those with diastolic dysfunction.

Comparative analysis between participants with and without diastolic dysfunction revealed significant differences in TSH and free T3 levels, with higher TSH (6.1 $\pm$ 1.3 vs. 5.6 $\pm$ 1.1, $p = 0.03$) and lower free T3 (3.0 $\pm$ 0.4 vs. 3.2 $\pm$ 0.5, $p = 0.04$)

in the diastolic dysfunction group. This suggests that higher levels of TSH and lower free T3 might be associated with the development of DD in SCH.

Overall, this study highlights a significant prevalence of LVDD among patients with SCH. The association between elevated TSH, reduced free T3, and diastolic dysfunction underscores the importance of regular cardiovascular screening and monitoring in this population. Early detection and management of diastolic dysfunction could potentially mitigate cardiovascular risks and improve outcomes in patients with SCH.

In SCH, the prevalence of left atrial dysfunction was examined in a study. 7.2% of participants in the study had SCH, and when compared to euthyroid individuals, these people showed significantly less left atrial reservoir and conduit strain. The independent correlation between SCH and reduced left atrial reservoir strain emphasises the subclinical effects of hypothyroidism on heart function [4].

A case-control study on patients with SCH was carried out to examine left ventricular diastolic dysfunction. 95 people participated in the study, which found that patients with SCH had higher A wave velocity, deceleration duration, isovolumic relaxation time, and decreased E wave velocity and E/A ratio. These results imply that diastolic dysfunction is significantly more common in SCH patients [5].

Levothyroxine therapy's effectiveness for treating diastolic dysfunction in SCH patients was evaluated in a study. Echocardiographic parameters such as E wave velocity, E/A ratio, and ejection

percent showed significant improvements in the study, which had 40 patients receiving levothyroxine treatment for a year. Levothyroxine medication was found to be an effective treatment for diastolic dysfunction in patients with SCH [6].

Studies looked into the connection between LVDD in patients with SCH and fragmented QRS (fQRS) on the ECG. According to the study, fQRS was more common in patients with SCH and was linked to longer isovolumic relaxation times and higher myocardial performance indices (MPIs), suggesting a higher risk of LVDD in these individuals [7].

A study examined how SCH affected the prognosis for heart failure. Compared to individuals with euthyroid hearts, those with SCH had significantly higher pulmonary arterial pressure and lower peak oxygen demand among 1100 heart failure patients. SCH's detrimental effects on heart function were highlighted when it was found to be a predictor of all-cause mortality and adverse cardiac events [8].

Conclusion

Subclinical hypothyroidism is associated with a higher prevalence of LVDD. Regular cardiovascular assessments should be considered in the management of patients with subclinical hypothyroidism to prevent potential cardiovascular complications.

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